

Review

Digital twins in safety analysis, risk assessment and emergency management

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ABSTRACT

Digital twins (DTs) represent an emerging technology that is currently leveraging the monitoring of complex systems, the implementation of autonomous control systems, and assistance during accidents and emergencies in real time. However, aspects such as safety, cybersecurity and reliability of DTs are still open issues that have not been comprehensively addressed. These aspects can offer new insights to evaluate the risk and return obtained from the implementation of DTs. This paper presents a systematic literature review of DTs focused on their use in safety analysis, risk assessment and emergency management. The aim of this work is twofold: (i) to point at the latest advancements in this technology by presenting a catalog of expected functions and twinning enabling technologies in the application domains of interest; and (ii) to point at the limitations and pending challenges on the implementation of DTs for safety analysis, risk assessment and emergency management.

1. Introduction

Digital Twins (DTs) have the potential to revolutionize decision-making and optimization processes by mirroring products and services and creating virtual copies of complex systems by leveraging real-time data, modeling, and simulation techniques [1]. DTs can support the development of new prototypes, monitor the state of assets, assist emergencies and accidents in real time, and perform control actions by mimicking the system dynamics through a digital replica, providing support throughout the whole lifecycle [2,3]. Numerous organizations have reported the potential of DT features in various fields with promising results, fueling interest and research in the technology [4,5].

One of the first documented DTs was conceived in the aerospace domain during the Apollo 13 program, where simulators on the ground mirrored the state of the crewed spacecraft. As stated by [6], DTs played a significant role when the spacecraft suffered an in-flight explosion, damaging the main engine and affecting the oxygen supplies. During the accident, the ground control used the simulators and data from the damaged spacecraft to explore contingency strategies, bringing the crew back safely. The term "Digital Twin" was first introduced by Grieves [7] in product lifecycle management to enhance product prototyping and design. The term "Digital Twin" was then used by NASA [8], emphasizing the use of modeling and simulation (M&S) to support the twinning

process of a system under a lifecycle perspective. Since then, DTs have received increasing attention in several sectors, including manufacturing, automotive, power, healthcare and information systems [5,9,10]. DTs have also been used for safety analysis and risk assessment, component health monitoring and predictive maintenance. DTs have proven to be effective in system performance monitoring [1,11], real-time control feedback [12,13] and optimization of manufacturing processes [14,15].

1.1. Motivation and research contribution

DTs can leverage not only the safety analysis and risk assessment, but also provide insights for a risk-informed decision-making process during accidents and emergencies. Yet, there is no current consensus when it comes to defining and characterizing a set of unique requirements for and expected outcomes from a DT [1,10]. Given the rapid increase of applications of DTs across different research domains, several reviews have been conducted in order to characterize the twinning process and define a set of technical requirements for its implementation. Tao et al. [1] and Huang et al. [16] reviewed the applications of DTs in production systems from the perspective of Industry 4.0 and smart manufacturing. Errandonea et al. [17] provided a systematic review of DTs for their use in maintenance applications. Later, van Dinter et al. [18] and You et al.

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[12] reviewed the state of the art of DTs in predictive maintenance, prognosis and health management applications. Agnusdei et al. [19] conducted a systematic review to analyze the use of DTs in the context of maintenance management. Thelen et al. [20] reviewed the models and twinning enabling techniques under a transdisciplinary approach. Similarly, Jones et al. [2] conducted a systematic review of DTs, introducing a new framework for their implementation and operation based on a lifecycle perspective.

Despite the wide variety of reviews and applications, there is a research gap regarding security and risk in the implementation of DTs. Aspects such as standardization, communication and data management protocols, cybersecurity and lifecycle persistence are just some of the open issues that need to be addressed, especially when it comes to applications in risk assessment and emergency management [21,22]. These aspects must be treated carefully, as they can offer new insights on how to evaluate the risk and return of implementing DTs. This article presents a critical review of DTs in the application domains of safety analysis, risk assessment and emergency management. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first systematic literature review that covers the three application domains mentioned above. The objectives of this study are twofold: (i) to point at the latest advancements in this technology, presenting a catalog of expected functions and twinning enabling technologies, and (ii) to point at the limitations and pending challenges on the implementation of DTs for safety analysis, risk assessment and emergency management. In this way, this article seeks to offer professionals and researchers an overview of the implementation of DTs in the selected application domains, identifying the supporting techniques and technologies, expected functions, and pending challenges in security aspects for future work.

The remainder of this paper is as follows: Section 2 provides technical requirements and essential aspects of DTs, highlighting the expected features for safety analysis, risk assessment and emergency management applications; Section 3 presents the methodology to conduct the SLR; Section 4 presents the results; Section 5 includes the discussion; Section 6 concludes with some final remarks.

2. Background

2.1. Digital twin modelling

2.1.1. Digital twin characterization

As the characterization of DTs evolves with time, several conceptual models for DTs have been incorporating a more detailed description of the constitutive entities and their relationship [1,7,9]. These conceptual models distinguish at least three fundamental entities:

1. **Physical Object (PO):** Also called "real space" [7], "physical twin" [23], or "physical system" [9]. The PO corresponds to the twinned system, which can represent a single component or a complex system with multiple interacting components [24]. The DT must collect data from the PO by integrating several data acquisition techniques.
2. **Digital Object (DO):** Also referred to as "virtual space" [7], "digital system" [23], or "virtual replica". The DO represents the ensemble of models and modules that mimics the state of the PO and its evolution in time. The state of the PO is typically a non-observable quantity and becomes intractable when modeling directly. The definition of the DO states must be carefully analyzed and respond to the DT use case and expected functions [25].
3. **The twinning process:** Corresponds to the seamless integration and communication feedback between the PO and the DO [26]. The PO and its corresponding DO should be intertwined to exchange information and perform monitoring and control functions. DTs must be equipped with an interface that allows data to flow bidirectionally in near-real-time in such a way that the PO adapts its condition according to control actions and optimal requirements. The twinning process can cover the feedforward and backward communication, i.

e., the physical-to-virtual (P2V) and the virtual-to-physical (V2P) processes, respectively. The nature and requirements of these interactions must be specified according to the expected features of the DT.

2.1.2. Conceptual models of digital twins

Some conceptual models for DTs explain the relationship between their constitutive elements, including the twinning process. Despite the abundance of definitions for DTs, there is no consensus to establish a conceptual model that can be agnostic for sectors and application domains. The most relevant conceptual models are:

- **Three-dimension model:** Originally proposed by Grieves [7], which introduced the first conceptual model for DTs by defining three essential entities: the PO, the DO and the bidirectional communication that feeds data (i.e., P2V twinning process) and enacts control actions (i.e., the V2P twinning process), establishing a closed feedback loop [2] (see Fig. 1.a);
- **Five-dimension models:**
 - i) Tao et al. [27] proposed a conceptual model for the manufacturing industry, composed of five dimensions. As proposed originally by Grieves, the model comprises a physical layer and a virtual layer to support the simulation, decision-making and control actions. This conceptual model includes the services provided to the users as a fundamental part of the DT (see Fig. 1. b). An iterative optimization process connects the three entities through the data exchange, representing a key element in the twinning process. In this way, the conceptual model proposes a DT composed of virtual entities, digital entities, services, data, and the connections among them;
 - ii) Thelen et al. [9] suggest a five-dimension conceptual model for DTs as an extension of the one proposed by Grieves. This conceptual model comprises a physical system (PS); a digital system (DS); an updating engine (P2V); a prediction engine (V2P); and an optimization engine (OPT). In this approach, the P2V engine updates the state of the DS based on the sensed data. The DS, composed of an ensemble of models, is then employed to predict the future state of the PS using the V2P engine, enabling predictive decision-making by feeding back the control actions to the PS through actuators. The OPT engine supports the functionalities of the other DT entities by optimizing data collection, state estimation, and reward functions (see Fig. 1.c).

2.1.3. The twinning process

2.1.3.1. Physical-to-virtual process. The P2V twinning represents the process of transferring the PO state into the virtual space. The P2V twinning process is performed by updating the virtual parameters to reflect the state of the PO. It is worth mentioning that the twinning process is characterized and formulated in different ways, depending on the conceptual model and the targeted application domain. According to Jones et al. [2], the P2V process includes two phases: the metrology phase, in which the PO state is estimated, and the realization phase, in which the deviation between the PO and the DO is quantified and the virtual entity is updated accordingly. This seamless integration between the physical and virtual spaces represents the main difference between DTs and traditional simulation techniques, where the data and information exchange are performed offline.

2.1.3.2. Data fusion. Data fusion techniques play an essential role in the twinning process, especially in the P2V twinning process [28]. Data fusion involves integrating data sources from multiple sensors or heterogeneous databases. Typically, the data supplied for fusion comprises several signals characterized by different resolutions and accuracies, while the databases may contain spurious, inconsistent, or incomplete

observations. Data fusion also includes processing and analysis to derive new insights and knowledge from observable data.

Data fusion techniques can address one of the three phases in the data fusion process: data association, state estimation and decision-level fusion [29]. Data association aims to establish consistency between the observations over time by using data-driven models for classification and debugging. Data association also includes the depuration of training data or the generation of simulated datasets for domain adaptation, which can support prognostics and anomaly detection tasks [30].

State estimation techniques aim to determine the hidden state variables of the PO based on the available observations and measurements. The estimation problem involves finding the values for state variables and parameters that best fit the observed data. Some estimation techniques include the use of surrogate models and Bayesian modeling to enhance state estimation accuracy.

Decision-level fusion aims to perform high-level inferences about the state of the PO and its expected functional output. These techniques

often leverage symbolic information obtained from the data while accounting for uncertainties, anomalies and feasibility constraints. In this way, decision-level fusion techniques are used to analyze the consistency of the DT by measuring the discrepancy between the PO and its corresponding DO [31,32].

2.1.3.3. *Virtual-to-physical process.* The V2P process must incorporate functionalities to update the state of the PO and ensure interoperability. This can be done by triggering changes in display terminals, programmable logic controllers (PLC), control systems, and operational parameters. The V2P can also contain both metrology and realization phases. The metrology phase aims to estimate the current state of the PO by using reward functions and feasibility constraints [5]. The realization phase seeks to determine the discrepancy between the desired and the current state of the PO, performing the control actions accordingly [2]. Several studies formulate a DO with a standalone P2V connection, keeping an uninterrupted continuous data stream from the PO to the DO,

Fig. 1. Digital Twin conceptual models. a) Three-dimension model [7]; b) Five-dimension model [27]; c) Five-dimension model [9].

and a discontinuous information flow from the DO to the PO (i.e., V2P twinning). In this case, the DO state only mimics the state of the PO in real-time, without performing the control actions automatically or autonomously. This is also conceived as a Digital Shadow (DS) [33]: as stated, the DS assimilates the data continuously, but the traffic of information from the DO to the PO is performed manually through an offline routine (Fig. 1). In control applications, the V2P twinning process can close the gap between the expected and current operating conditions in the physical layer.

2.2. Implementation of digital twins

The essential functionality of a DT is the twinning process itself, giving rise to a closed feedback process using low-latency data streams between the PO and the DO [34]. One of the fundamental questions is how to implement a DT to meet the technical and functional requirements. In this regard, several reference models for the implementation of DTs have been proposed in the literature. For example, the reference models proposed by Lu et al. [32] and Bevilacqua et al. [3,35] responded to the specific needs of manufacturing and processing plants, within the context of Industry 4.0. On the other hand, some reference models addressed the implementation and requirements of DTs across different industries. Bönsch et al. [36] defined a subject-oriented reference model, focusing on the interaction between the PO, the DO, the users and the administrators of DTs. Newrzella et al. [37] proposed a reference model for the architecture of DTs based on functionality, dependability, and lifecycle development. Other studies proposed a set of requirements for DTs by tackling specific topics, such as the use of dynamic models and simulation methods for the P2V twinning process [38,39]. Despite the recent efforts to standardize the implementation of DTs, this topic remains an open issue for future research.

2.2.1. Expected features for digital twins in selected application domains

Several studies [1,9,40] have proposed a set of expected features to distinguish DTs from other technologies; however, the analysis being held in those works establishes a general overview for several application domains. In this section, we summarize the expected features of DTs for safety analysis, risk assessment and emergency management:

- **Lifecycle dependency:** The DT must be aligned with the lifecycle of the twinned system, from design to decommission or disposal. In this way, the DT is evolving along with the system, capturing and storing information throughout the lifecycle of the PO. In this sense, the DT must ensure reliability, confidentiality and security for organizations and users [14]. Model validation becomes an open issue to overcome the challenges of trustworthy technologies for users and decision-makers, including information about the environment, infrastructures, and human resources. As stated, data-driven algorithms have difficulties dealing with contextual information and off-scale data points. On the other hand, Reinforcement Learning (RL) techniques can be adapted automatically, but they can be computationally demanding when responding to accidents and disruptions. Integrating data-driven and physics-based models can offer new capabilities for data assimilation in real-time [41].
- **Modularity:** To respond under disruptive events or accidental scenarios, a data stream must be assimilated by the DT model repository. This data stream can feed an ensemble of multi-scale, multi-physics and multi-fidelity models. In this sense, models can be classified with respect to either the physical knowledge dependence or the use of data to estimate or predict the system behavior [42]. White-Box (WB) models, also known as physics-based models, depend exclusively on the physical knowledge, establishing a trade-off between accuracy and interpretability [43]; conversely, Black-Box (BB) models use and process data at the expense of direct interpretability and expert-based understanding of the model output

[44]. For this reason, the modularity of DTs can be crucial to exploit the capabilities of data assimilation and physics-based models.

- **Uncertainty quantification:** DTs need a proper interface and repository to support the ensemble of models and perform data analytics. The internal data assimilation process of the DT requires a noise-free, uninterrupted data stream [14]. The aleatory uncertainty of observable data and epistemic uncertainty must be identified and quantified. Therefore, a VVUQ (Verification, Validation, and Uncertainty Quantification) module must be developed to quantify the sources of uncertainty in safety-critical applications [13,11]. Given the combination of discrete and continuous signals and processes, the latency and refreshing time represent a significant challenge for an effective DT, especially for risk assessment.
- **Interpretability and explainability:** The implementation of DTs in safety-critical infrastructures and emergency management must comply with strict regulations by providing trustworthy information that supports the decision-making process [45]. These requirements establish new challenges for transparency and explainability of ML techniques. Although physics-based models usually enable extrapolation capabilities, they often bring high computational costs. Data-driven models lower the computational burden, but their extrapolation capabilities depend on the training dataset, which may not be fully consistent with the physical behavior of the system in all operating conditions [42]. Grey-Box (GB) and hybrid models can offer a trade-off between accuracy, computational cost, and interpretability by combining the use of WB and BB models [43,46]. Explainable AI (XAI) techniques can also offer new insights for improving the transparency of BB models, providing explainable arguments for the output of ML-based methods [47].

3. Methodology

We adopted the guidelines of semi-automatic SLRs as proposed in van Dinter et al. [18], allowing reproducibility and bias reduction [48]. The proposed methodology for the SLR is depicted in Fig. 2 and covers the following steps: definition of Research Questions (RQs); definition of search strategy; search process; and application of specific selection and evaluation criteria.

3.1. Definition of research questions

This study addresses the RQs proposed in Table 1 to guide the selection of primary studies. The formulation of the RQs is aligned with the Objectives proposed in Section 1 to identify the limitations and challenges for each application domain.

3.2. Search scope

This review aimed to collect studies, including journal papers and conference papers published between 2018 and 2023, i.e., comprising a period of more than five years. The studies were searched in the following main electronic databases: Scopus and Web of Science (WoS).

3.3. Search methods and strings

We used a semi-automated literature search method, scanning search strings in electronic databases, without supporting the search process with backward and forward snowballing. The following search strings were included for the scanning of each application domain of interest: (“digital twin” AND “risk assessment”); (“digital twin” AND “safety analysis”); (“digital twin” AND (“accident” OR “emergency” OR “accidents” OR “emergencies”)). We searched for the relevant literature by using the text strings for each application domain (i.e., safety analysis, risk assessment and emergency management). We looked for the selected search strings in the title, abstract and keywords, for each database and application domain.

Fig. 2. Schematics of the systematic literature review.

Table 1
Research questions.

No.	Research question (RQ)
RQ1	What are the expected tasks or functions covered by Digital Twins, when applied to safety analysis, risk assessment and emergency management?
RQ2	Which techniques and approaches are being applied for the implementation of Digital Twins in safety analysis, risk assessment and emergency management domains?
RQ3	Which types of model representations for Digital Twins are being applied to safety analysis, risk assessment and emergency management domains?
RQ4	Which aspects of the twinning process are being taken into consideration for the implementation of Digital Twins in these specific application domains?
RQ5	What are the limitations and challenges for the development of Digital Twins in these application domains?

3.4. Study selection criteria

The selection criteria included a set of inclusion and exclusion rules (see Table 2). To support the selection of primary studies after applying the inclusion (IC) and exclusion criteria (EC), the selection was performed by a data-driven SLR automation tool [18]. The selection criteria were applied by analyzing both title and abstract for each study. After filtering the preliminary search, we merged the obtained databases for each application domain, discarding duplicates.

3.5. Evaluation criteria

After the first screening, the studies were filtered again by reading and analyzing the work proposed in each study. The final selection was conducted by following the ICs (see Table 2). The selected studies were considered for further analysis and discussion in Section 4.

4. Results

After the application of the evaluation criteria, the selected studies were carefully analyzed to address the proposed RQs systematically.

Table 2
Inclusion and exclusion criteria.

No.	Criterion
IC1	The study must provide a full text (e.g., abstract-only papers will not be considered)
IC2	The article must be a primary study
IC3	The study proposes a case study, framework, or applied methodology for the implementation of Digital Twins in one of the following application domains: safety analysis, risk assessment and emergency management
EC1	The study is duplicated
EC2	The study belongs to non-English language publications

This section is divided into two subsections: first, we present an overview of the results; secondly, a detailed discussion of the response to the RQs is conducted.

4.1. Overview

A quantitative overview of the application of the methodology is given in Table 3 in terms of the number of studies for each application domain. After merging the databases generated for each application domain, the evaluation criteria were applied consistently. The list of selected studies after applying the evaluation criteria is presented in Table 4. The following subsection is devoted to the RQs proposed for the primary studies for each application domain.

4.2. Research question 1: expected tasks and functions

Table 5 presents a summary of the expected tasks and functions by application domain. In safety analysis, most of the DT-based methods are used to leverage the analysis of safety influencing factors and safety assessment performance. Regarding the industrial fields of application, most of the case studies are related to construction, naval engineering and manufacturing. In risk assessment applications, the studies showed a variety of expected tasks and functions, highlighting risk monitoring, failure prognostics and fault diagnosis. Many of the case studies are related to the manufacturing and construction industries. In accident and emergency management applications, DTs have been used for several tasks in various industrial fields such as automotive, construction and warehouse operations.

4.3. Research question 2: model representation types

Table 6 summarizes the model representation types categorized by application domain. The main findings are described below:

- Safety analysis:** The model representations in this application domain vary according to the expected functional output of the DT and the industrial field. Geometric models and Finite Element (FE) methods were used to build the DO within the digital layer [49–51]. In these cases, the DO is updated by tuning the parameters of the physics-based models to match the observable data. In other studies, physics-based models are combined with data-driven models for data assimilation, giving rise to hybrid models [52,54,55]. Under this approach, data-driven models can preprocess or transform the data to be assimilated by the physics-based model representation.
- Risk assessment:** The model representations used to implement the DT vary according to the industrial field of application. In construction and manufacturing applications, geometric models were

Table 3
Overview of systematic literature review.

Application domain	After automated search		After selection criteria		After selection criteria (merged)	After evaluation criteria (merged)
	Scopus	WoS	Scopus	WoS		
Safety analysis	42	19	20	9	19	9
Risk assessment	203	75	66	29	40	24
Emergency management	171	61	31	12	19	7

Table 4
List of selected studies after evaluation criteria.

Application domain	Selected studies after evaluation criteria
Safety analysis	[49–57]
Risk assessment	[15,25,30,58–78]
Emergency management	[79–85]

Table 5
Summary of research question 1.

Application domain	RQ1: Expected tasks and functions	RQ1: Industrial field of application
Safety Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Calculation of safety influencing factors [49,50] • Safety assessment performance [51–53] • Stability analysis [54] • Identification of hazardous effects and accidents [54] • Real-time visual warning system [55] • Safety poka-yoke methods for manufacturing processes [56] • Monitoring and analysis of occupational safety [57] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction and civil engineering [49–52,54,55] • Naval engineering [53] • Manufacturing processes [56,57]
Risk Assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk identification [58] • Quantitative risk assessment [59,60] • General risk assessment [61] • Risk and reliability assessment [62–64] • Driving risk assessment [65] • Safety risk factors [66,67] • Prognostics [68,69–71] • Risk monitoring [15,72,73] • Risk forecasting [74] • Fault diagnosis [75–78,30] • Monitoring and control [25] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automotive industry [65] • Robotics [25] • Power grids [59,60] • Nuclear engineering [15] • Manufacturing [30,61,69,71] • Construction [58,62–64,66] • Multidisciplinary [74] • Mining industry [68] • Construction [67,72] • Oil and gas [73] • Mechanical engineering [75–78] • Maritime engineering [70]
Emergency Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lighting schedule for real-time guidance during accidents [79] • Tracking solution framework for safety management under emergencies [80] • DT-assisted cooperative driving [81] • Integrated framework for situational awareness during emergencies [82] • Prediction and prevention of traffic accidents [83] • Analysis of a building collapse accident [84] • Smart guided pedestrian evacuation system for simulated accidents [85] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Warehouse operations [80] • Autonomous driving [81] • Disaster City Digital Twin [82] • Automotive industry [83] • Construction [79,84,85]

combined with remote sensors for generating the virtual replica [61–64,72]; other studies described the use of hybrid models, combining ML techniques and physics-based models under several configurations. ML techniques were used to update the parameters or

state variables of the physics-based models [15,65]; in other cases, a physics-based simulator delivered the information to the ML model to predict state variables or risk metrics of the twinned system [60,68].

In risk monitoring and control applications, the implementation of DTs was often supported by an ensemble of physics-based and data-driven models such as advanced ML techniques and TL [69–71,75–78]. This approach tackles the need to integrate observational data with previous knowledge about the PO. In those studies, physics-based models provided key information for domain adaptation, supporting classification tasks in abnormality detection and fault classification.

- **Emergency management:** Physics-based models and geometric models for simulation were mainly used for construction applications [79,84,85]. Geometric models and VR techniques have been exploited in the automotive industry to support the implementation of human-machine interfaces (HMIs) [81,83]. In other case studies, metaheuristics and ML techniques have been used in combination with mathematical models and data-driven models, respectively, giving rise to hybrid models for risk monitoring [80,82].

4.4. Research question 3: techniques and approaches for the implementation of digital twins

Table 6 summarizes the specific techniques and approaches used for DT implementation. The review provided the following main findings:

- **Safety analysis:** A wide variety of techniques were used to support the implementation of DTs. Tools such as Building Information Model (BIM) and FE-based software were widely applied to support the P2V twinning process and facilitate the interaction with the PO [50–52,54]. Techniques such as Markov Chains, Bow-tie method, and FMECA have been used to support the safety performance assessment [51,53].
- **Risk assessment:** In risk assessment applications, machine vision algorithms were used in the automotive industry to extract microscopic traffic flow information [58,65]. ML techniques were used for semantic segmentation and the prediction of critical variables [68,74]. The implementation of the digital layer has also been supported by physics-based models, such as geometric and FE models [64,65]. Regarding applications in fault diagnosis, physics-based simulation models were used with ML data-driven models for online classification [69]. Hybrid models were used for fault diagnosis in scarce labeled data scenarios [30,75,76,78]. The implementation of hybrid models for DTs has also been conducted for prognostics, exploiting techniques such as FE methods [69,70], Random Forests and XG Boost [71].
- **Emergency management:** This application domain included the use of VR, BIMs and ML techniques. Other studies proposed the integration of metaheuristics and data-driven models for early-warning and emergency management systems [80,82].

4.5. Research question 4: twinning process

RQ4 attempts to clarify the fundamental aspects of the twinning process in the selected studies. In particular, the data management, communication and connectivity, and the expected functional output of

Table 6
Summary of Research Questions 2 and 3.

Application domain	RQ2: Model representation types	RQ3: Techniques and approaches for the implementation of DT
Safety Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physics-based models <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Geometric models [50,51] ◦ Mechanical models [52,55] ◦ Thermohydraulic models [54] • Data-driven models [57,58] • Ensemble of physics-based and data-driven models [53,56] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High-fidelity simulation models [50,51] • Finite element methods <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ ANSYS [52] • Building Information Models [53,55] • ML techniques: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Active learning deep neural networks (AL-DNNs), domain adversarial neural networks (DANNs), [57] ◦ LSTM [53] ◦ Stacked Autoencoder (SAE) [57,58] ◦ Virtual reality and deep learning [56] • Risk models: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ FMECA [54] ◦ Bow-Tie [52] • Machine vision [59,66] • Simulation models: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ 3D simulation models [61,73] ◦ Discrete event simulation [62] ◦ Physics-based simulation [69,76] ◦ Thermohydraulics [15] ◦ Multi-physics simulation [79] • ML techniques: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ DL for semantic segmentation [63,64] ◦ Neural networks [61] ◦ LSTM [75] ◦ QGNN [69] ◦ Random Forests [72] ◦ XG Boost [72] ◦ Deep transfer learning [78] ◦ PCA [74] ◦ SVM [74] • Finite element methods [65,71,72] • Building information models [67,68] • Dynamic Bayesian Networks [25] • Simulation models: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Virtual Reality [80] ◦ Augmented Reality [82] ◦ Other [86] • ML techniques: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ LSTM [84] ◦ PF [84] ◦ DAM and SLGP [81] • FE methods [85] • Building information models [85]
Risk Assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geometric models [65,73] • Physics-based models [65] • Information models [60,62] • Data-driven models [59,75,74] • Ensemble of physics-based and data-driven models [61,69,15,70,71,72,30,76,77,78,79] • Ensemble of geometric and data-driven models [63,64,67,68,66] • Graphical models [25] 	
Emergency Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physics-based models [80,85] • Geometric models [82,86] • Information models [85] • Data-driven models [81] • Hybrid models [83,84] 	

DTs were analyzed in detail (see Table 7). The main findings include the following aspects:

- **Safety analysis:** The articles described technical aspects of data collection, integration and assimilation. Most of the studies addressed aspects of the data collection, using remotely sensed data for the twinning process. Several protocols for communication and connectivity are described, highlighting the use of wireless network technology and IoT-based communication. In most applications, the expected functional output of the twinning process was the calculation of safety indicators for monitoring and visualization.
- **Risk assessment:** Data collection and assimilation were the most relevant topics, highlighting the use of observational data and ML techniques, respectively. Regarding communication and connectivity protocols, wireless networks and IoT-based infrastructures were used for data transmission. The expected functional output for DTs included: visualization, monitoring of critical variables, and the implementation of control systems.

Some studies described the V2P twinning process using a closed feedback loop for control purposes [66,67]. In [72], the V2P connection allows the activation of safety protocols and response plans based on the evolution of risk indicators. Regarding fault diagnosis and prognosis applications, the tools used to support the twinning process were not described in detail. Since there is no closed communication loop, these applications correspond to digital

shadows, which allow the incorporation of relevant information about the PO into the DO through offline routines.

- **Emergency management:** The reviewed articles described data collection and assimilation processes. While data collection was essentially supported by the use of remote sensors, data assimilation included the integration of VR, IIoT-based devices, and ML models to extract useful information. Most of the studies conceived DTs for monitoring safety variables and indicators, and visualizing the state of systems and critical infrastructure.

Unlike the application domains described above, some studies proposed the use of DTs for validation and testing purposes [79,84,85]. In these cases, the expected functions of the DO did not require an uninterrupted and real-time connection of data and information between the PO and the DO. In [84], the DO integrated information about the collapsed building to analyze the underlying causes that triggered the accident. In [85], the DT was used to test and simulate several strategies for the evacuation system by following a post-hoc analysis.

4.6. Research question 5: limitations and challenges

The last RQ addresses the limitations and challenges related to the implementation of DTs, with particular emphasis on safety and risk. Table 8 describes the trends and challenges identified from the review. The most relevant topics are summarized below:

Table 7
Summary of Research Question 4.

Application domain	RQ4: Data management	RQ4: Communication protocols and connectivity	RQ4: Expected functional output of the DT
Safety Analysis	<p>Data collection</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of sensors [51,52,55,53,56,54,57,58] Use of simulated and sensed data [50] <p>Data integration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information management and control platform [51] Data acquisition system [54] <p>Data assimilation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of Dempster-Shafer evidence theory [50] Use of DL [56] Use of ML techniques [57] 	<p>Communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wireless network technology [52,55] IoT based communication [53,58] Workshop management and control system [57] <p>Connectivity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Industrial 485 communication protocol [55] TCP protocol [56] BLE wireless protocol [58] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitoring and visualization [50,52,53,55,56] Monitoring and optimization of maintenance strategies [51] Monitoring and control [54] Early warning and control [57] Visualization and early warning [58]
Risk Assessment	<p>Data collection</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of sensors [15,25,30,60,63,64,69,66,59,67,68,73,74,76,77,78,79,70,72] Use of available datasets [62,75,71] <p>Data preprocessing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Posture perception algorithms [65] <p>Data integration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of cloud servers [67,68] Use of IoT smart modules and cloud servers [74] <p>Data assimilation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of DL for semantic segmentation [63] Use of NNs [61] Update of electric field FE model [65] ML methods for prediction [75,69] Geometric models update [67,68] Use of ML methods and ROMs [15] Machine vision [66] Domain adaptation networks [30] Dynamic Bayesian Network [25] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not founded [15,30,60,62,63,65,69,66,59,75,76,77,78,79,70,71,72] <p>Communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of SCADA architecture [61] Wireless network [67,74,25] Wireless sensor networks [73] <p>Connectivity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of HTTP requests and API calls [64] LoRA technology supported by 4G network [68] WPA encryption and wireless protocols [74] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Real-time monitoring of traffic risks [59] Visualization and decision-making [60,62] Monitoring and visualization [15,63,64,65,66,75,67,68,76,77,78,79,70,71,72] Monitoring and control [61,69,25] Real-time monitoring and emergency management [73] Monitoring and prediction of risk probability [74] Condition monitoring assessment [30]
Emergency management	<p>Data collection</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of sensors [80,86,81,83,84] Use of available datasets [82,85] <p>Data assimilation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integration of ML and VR [80] ML techniques [81] Motion control algorithms and HMI [82] ML techniques with 3D geometric modeling [84] 	<p>Communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not founded [80,85,86,83,82,84] Wireless network [81] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Validation and test [80,85,86] Monitoring and visualization [81,83,84] Monitoring and control [82]

- Uncertainty quantification:** Given that DTs require a noise-free stream of data, it is necessary to quantify the aleatory and epistemic uncertainties in order to estimate the variability in the functional output of the DT. This aspect is critical across all application domains to ensure the consistency and effectiveness of decision-making based on the information retrieved by the DT. Despite the use of sensed data and the implementation of data-driven models, there is no evidence of uncertainty quantification techniques to support DTs in risk analysis, risk assessment and emergency management applications.
- Consistency and persistence:** DT consistency is critical for risk-based decision-making, as it guarantees that the information provided mirrors the current state of the PO. On the other hand, persistence allows DTs to maintain their functionality over time, regardless of the current state of the PO. Even during failures or accidents, a persistent DT can still be able to perform continuous monitoring, analysis, and control actions. The pending challenge is the generation of persistent DTs for managing accidents and emergencies in real-time, so that the DO can mimic the state of components and critical infrastructures along the accident dynamics for delivering control actions and mitigation strategies.
- Cybersecurity and threat identification:** Ensuring cybersecurity and managing data quality are significant challenges in the implementation of DTs across all the selected application domains. The current challenge is to identify the threats and vulnerabilities associated with the implementation of DTs, focusing on the functionality layers and operational requirements. There is a need for a systematic and complete classification of potential threats to balance the risk and return of DT implementation.
- V2P twinning process:** In risk assessment and emergency management applications, there are limitations regarding V2P communication protocols and devices to ensure a seamless connection between the DO and the PO. Although the data fusion process and P2V twinning are widely addressed, only a few applications described the V2P twinning process consistently. In such cases, the applications were fundamentally related to optimization and control in real-time by means of a closed feedback loop. There are still some challenges to determining how the information can be seamlessly transferred to update contingency strategies without the intervention of operators.
- Standardization:** In risk assessment applications, it is not clear how to perform the data collection nor the requirements to generate an

Table 8
Summary of detected trends and pending challenges.

Application domain	RQ5: Detected trends and issues	RQ5: Pending challenges
Safety analysis	<p>Model representation types</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integration of physics-based and ML models <p>Data integration and transmission</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of sensors for data collection Data integration with information and BIM platforms Use of wireless networks for data transmission 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Uncertainty quantification Interoperability Consistency and persistence Cybersecurity and threat identification
Risk assessment	<p>Model representation types</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of domain adaptation and TL techniques for fault identification and diagnosis Integration of physics-based and ML models <p>Data integration and transmission</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of sensors for data collection Scarcity of labeled data Use of wireless networks for data transmission Use of cloud servers for data integration <p>Twinning process</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scarcity of online tests for DTs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Uncertainty quantification Consistency and persistence Cybersecurity and threat identification V2P twinning process for control Standardization of P2V and V2P communication protocols
Emergency management	<p>Model representation types</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integration of physics-based and ML models <p>Data integration and transmission</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integration of VR tools, HMI, and IoT-based devices Use of cloud servers for data integration <p>Twinning process</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of DTs for validation and testing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Uncertainty quantification Interoperability Consistency and persistence Cybersecurity and threat identification V2P twinning process for early warning and emergency management

online, real-time routine for DTs. Most studies addressed aspects of data assimilation and the calculation of safety indicators supported by DTs. However, there is a lack of communication protocols to establish how this information can be transferred to the PO during operation. Online monitoring and communication play an essential role in risk assessment and accident management, such as the integration of DTs into existing emergency management systems.

- Interoperability:** Interoperability must be carefully analyzed in safety analysis and emergency management applications. Given that several studies described the integration of DTs with information and control platforms, the virtual layer must be able to ensure interoperability and communication with other existing systems. A thorough safety analysis and threat identification must be conducted carefully, as such integration can eventually lead to new vulnerabilities.

4.7. Illustrative examples

This section presents some illustrative examples to explain the

methodology and describe the systematic implementation of DTs. We present two case studies, taken from risk assessment applications, based on the completeness of the RQs.

4.7.1. A DT-based methodology for safety assessment of building hoistings

Liu et al. [66,67] proposed the implementation of a DT for the safety assessment of building hoistings. In this study, the DT was used to support the identification of potential risks and suggest corrective measures. The RQs for this case study are summarised in Table 9. The DT was systematically implemented by following the five-dimension conceptual model (see Fig. 3).

4.7.2. Digital twin-based early warning and safety management platform

Ye et al. [72] proposed a DT-based platform to support the safety management of a tunnel construction site and avoid potential accidents. The DT is intended to support functions such as real-time synchronization of the DO and site construction data, early warning and emergency management. The application of the RQs for the case study is summarised in Table 10. As in [67], the case study presented in [72] systematically applies the conceptual model shown in Fig. 3.

5. Discussion

In the following subsections, aspects related to the consistency and validity of the methodology applied for SLR are discussed, and subsequently, the limitations and pending challenges extracted from the studies.

5.1. Consistency and validity of the method

The following aspects of the methodology should be discussed:

- Reproducibility:** In order to ensure reproducibility in the selection and treatment of the selected articles, the SLR attempts to describe the key stages in the implementation of the methodology. However, there are relevant biases that can affect the final results of the SLR,

Table 9
Summary of research questions in the illustrative example 1.

Journal Papers	Liu et al. [66,67]
RQ1 - Proposed application domain RQ1 - Expected tasks and functions	Risk monitoring and control. Analysis and monitoring of safety risk factors; control of building hoisting operations.
RQ1 - Industrial field of application RQ2 - Model representation types	Construction. Building hoisting operations. Virtual representation of the hoisting building operation site supported by BIM; Use of data-driven methods for coupling of risk factors
RQ3 - Techniques and approaches for the implementation of Digital Twins	Data acquisition and transmission: Implementation of an IoT-based architecture with a self-organizing network. PO: A 3D geometric model of the building site supported by BIM was used. Data assimilation: Calculation and visualization of coupling safety factors. The method combined the Apriori algorithm, an unsupervised ML method for association relationship mining, and the use of complex networks for monitoring and control.
RQ4 - Twinning process	The DT is conducted by following a five-dimension conceptual model. The P2V twinning is supported with an IoT-based architecture and BIM for further data assimilation. Formulation of an online routine for real-time V2P twinning, closing the feedback loop. The loop is attempted to be closed with a control module, using a Bayesian Network to visualize and monitor the state of the risk factors in real-time.

Fig. 3. Implementation of conceptual models for DTs. a) Illustrative example 1; b) Illustrative example 2.

including the selection and combination of keywords, the application of the inclusion, exclusion and evaluation criteria, as well as the formulation of the RQs.

- Active learning process: This study employs an active learning method for the prioritization of relevant articles. Although the above facilitates the search process, it does not remove the biases induced by the reviewers during the selection process.
- Classification of the reviewed articles: In some exceptional cases, the primary studies addressed aspects of two application domains simultaneously. For example, some studies addressed aspects related to risk monitoring of critical variables, supporting an early warning system for emergency response plans. In this case, these studies can be either classified into risk monitoring or emergency management applications. The classification of the articles in each application domain is determined during the search process and the application of first selection criteria.

- Evaluation and selection of research questions: The RQs were carefully formulated in order to address essential aspects related to the state of the art in the selected application domains. It is relevant to emphasize the difficulty in extracting information from articles to answer certain RQs. Especially in the case of RQ5, some articles did not describe in detail the challenges derived from their own research process. The reviewers extracted the answer from the critical analysis of the texts, which may inevitably include biases in the results.

5.2. Limitations and challenges extracted from the reviewed literature

The challenges obtained from the systematic review are consistent with some of the features required for DTs in the selected application domains (Section 2.2.1). The review verifies the use of GB and hybrid models for the implementation of the DO and data processing. However, the reviewed studies do not discuss aspects related to uncertainty

Table 10
Summary of research questions in the illustrative example 2.

Journal Paper	Ye et al. [72]
RQ1 - Proposed classification	Risk monitoring and control.
RQ1 - Expected tasks and functions	Digital twin-based early warning and safety management platform.
RQ1 - Application domain	Construction. Tunnel engineering.
RQ2 - Model representation types	Geometric models.
RQ3 - Techniques and approaches for the implementation of Digital Twins	Data acquisition and transmission: Use of a wireless sensor network (WSN). Multi-source information of the construction site can be automatically sent and received by the platform, including sensed variables such as temperature, humidity, and gas concentration. The information collected is sent to the monitoring center by means of GPRS through a wireless transmission link. DO: 3D geometric model, based on the OpenGL platform. The DO is also able to assimilate real-time updated advanced geological prediction information and construction progress.
RQ4 - Twinning process	The DT is conducted by following a five-dimension conceptual model. The P2V twinning includes the use of multi-source information supported by IoT architecture. The PO is virtually simulated, assimilating real-time data about tunnel operations and environmental conditions. The V2P twinning considers the real-time monitoring of risk indicators. The risk indicators support a real-time four-level early warning system, which can activate emergency plans accordingly, closing the feedback loop between the DO and the PO.

quantification, consistency, and the use of XAI techniques to evaluate the expected functional output of DTs.

This work also adds new challenges obtained from the SLR, including the standardization, interoperability, cybersecurity, and the development of methodologies for V2P communication in control and emergency management functions in real time. It should be noted that these challenges are obtained in order to evaluate security and risk in the implementation of DTs; therefore, other technical aspects such as data management are not analyzed in detail.

6. Conclusions

This paper presents a critical review of DTs for their application to safety analysis, risk assessment and emergency management. The main DT conceptual models are analyzed, and the main challenges and cutting-edge techniques are described. Implementation aspects and expected features are reviewed with reference to the application domains.

The proposed methodology for the selection of primary studies is systematically applied. The selected articles are analyzed and discussed based on the RQs stated in the methodology. The analysis discusses the main supporting technologies for the twinning process and tools and approaches used for data fusion and assimilation in the virtual space. Particularly, the advancements in real-time emergency and risk assessment demonstrate the benefits of using DTs. However, there are major challenges that must be addressed to consolidate the development of this technology. Some insights and recommendations for future research are proposed below:

- One of the challenges is the seamless integration of DTs with existing systems and processes. Ensuring that DTs can communicate and share data with existing systems and methods can be a complex task, as it may require the development of new interfaces and protocols. It is crucial to ensure that data is being shared effectively so that it can be used to support decision-making and control tasks. For this,

organizations must carefully plan and invest resources to ensure that the integration process is being conducted effectively and efficiently, establishing secure communication protocols, and ensuring interoperability to fully exploit this technology.

- There is a lack of unified models or generic DT architectures in the literature, with no guidelines about how to build a DT at industrial scale. The data exchange between the DO and the interaction between components that shape the PO is not well developed so far; future work must consider the development of methodologies and protocols to integrate the massive data streams coming from heterogeneous sensors and complex systems. Another major challenge is the absence of standardization, showing discrepancies in the objectives and results for projects devoted to DTs. Establishing some benchmark problems and facilitating the evidence in data and DT replicability can boost the development of DT-based technologies.
- Another issue that must be considered is the role of operators and users in using and implementing DTs. In many cases, the studies do not address the decision-making process and the application of control actions, which corresponds to the V2P connection. In some cases, the role of the operator may be crucial to close the loop. In other cases, the V2P twinning process must be automated to exploit the potential of a DT, ensuring its autonomy and allowing its interaction with other assets and DTs. In this sense, a sequential decision problem approach and the use of model predictive control techniques may eventually offer an option to close the feedback loop. As emerged from the critical analysis of the literature review, it becomes challenging to separate the DT and V2P twinning concept from other traditional techniques, such as multi-physics simulation and modeling approaches, where the latter can represent an instance of the DO with a predefined set of inputs, conditions, and feasibility constraints for the implementation of DTs.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Enrico Zio: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Leonardo Miqueles:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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